

White Paper

Task Force 1: Interactions with users

Topic A:

Acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions to the end-users

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Document information

Contributors

First name	Last name	Organisation
Co-Chairs		
Alain	Zarli	ECTP
Vladimir	Gumilar	SGG
Task Force members		
Jaakko	Ketomäki	MOTIVA
Miimu	Airaksinen	RIL
Alexis	David	ECTP
Tristan	Emich	KIT
Peter	D'Herdt	BBRI
Joanna	Syrda	ASM
Agnieszka	Kowalska	ASM
Sami	Kazi	VTT
Natalie	Samovich	Enercoutim
Sylvain	Kubicki	LIST
Olivia	Guerra Santin	TUE
Helianthe	Kort	TUE
Calin	Boje	LIST
Peter	Richner	EMPA
Marta Maria	Sesana	POLIMI
Nerea	Gomez	ECTP
Marco	Barbagelata	STAM
Andrei Vladimir	Litiu	REHVA
Clémentine	Coujard	DOWEL Innovation
Reviewers		
Evi	Lambie	VITO
Birgit	Vandeveldde	VITO
Feedback from open consultation		
Daniela	Baer	SINTEF

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Executive summary

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating issues related to smart buildings: their objective is to identify the remaining challenges and barriers to smart building deployment, and the associated research and innovation gaps that should be addressed in the near future.

*Task force 1 investigates how the interactions between any smart building and its users can be facilitated and improved, as a key success factor for the market uptake of smart building solutions. The first topic addressed by this task force and presented in this paper is **Acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions for the end users.***

Smart building solutions are a strong leverage for increased energy efficiency in buildings, improved quality of life for occupants and added value for work performance, but only if those solutions are correctly understood and adopted by end users. While numerous smart solutions are being developed for the building sector, they are often designed following a technology-push approach, insufficiently taking into account the actual behaviors of building users and occupants, their expectations in terms of building features and functionalities, but also their reluctance or fears related to Information technologies, in particular the loss of privacy and control. This White paper focuses therefore on the following questions:

- What is our state of knowledge on building users' expectations, preferences and behaviours?
- Which of their specificities constitute major barriers or success factors to design fit-for-use smart building products?
- What technical and non-technical solutions can increase the acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions?

In its first part, this paper provides a state of the art regarding the following issues, specific attention being paid to EC-funded projects:

- **Knowledge of users: understanding of social behaviours and market knowledge** (technology acceptance model, knowledge gained about the "ageing in place" requirements and about building user behaviours and influencing factors)
- **Workflows and communication to raise acceptance and attractiveness** (user-centred and co-design, gamification)
- **Technical solutions to raise acceptance and attractiveness** (human user interfaces, crowdsensing)

A brainstorming process enabled to identify some key barriers and drivers regarding the acceptance of smart building solutions by end users. The next diagrams provide an overview of the main barriers and drivers discussed.

BARRIERS	
TECHNICAL	Weak adaptability of buildings to different end-users` profiles and to their different life phases in the building (e.g. moving in, getting used to the equipment...)
ECONOMIC	Economic concerns for end-user, occupant, private investor and owner: affordability/short term, compared to benefits (medium to long-term)
SOCIAL	Fears related to lack of data privacy and lack of control on smart solutions
	Unknown, different perceptions of comfort for different end-users wrt smart building use
VALUE CHAIN	Lock-in effect: how the smart solutions will evolve in the future, requirements for updates, upgrades
	Difficulties to implemented successful co-design processes with end-users in order to develop more user-centered products

} *Top barriers according to the Task Force*

Figure 1: Overview of main barriers

DRIVERS	
VALUE CHAIN	Implementation and capitalisation on new approaches for collaborative design, such as design thinking, co-creation processes, mental models considerations
	Best-practices in current projects related to gerontechnology and ageing in homes
SOCIAL	Increasing knowledge of building user behaviours and requirements on specific segments (elderly people at home, students in university buildings)
	Leverage on specific groups of people with most interest in providing feedback on SB solutions, like elderly people wishing to age in place
TECHNICAL	Good practices for the development IoT and AI-based apps, featuring easy-for-all and adaptative user experience

} *Top drivers according to the Task Force*

Figure 2: Overview of main drivers

Based on the State of the Art and the barriers and drivers, a number of research and innovation gaps were identified. They are synthetised in the next two diagrams.

Figure 3: R&I gaps

Figure 4: "Go-to-market" gaps

The gaps identified above will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

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1. Introduction

The SmartBuilt4EU project has set up four task forces investigating topics related to smart buildings. They respectively address the interaction between building and end-user, efficient building operation, interactions between the building and the external environment, and cross cutting issues.

Figure 5: The four Task Forces set up by the SmartBuilt4EU project

SmartBuilt4EU task force 1 investigates how the interactions between any smart building and its users can be facilitated and improved, as a key success factor for the market uptake of smart building solutions.

This investigation follows three main lines, so far defined as follows:

- **TOPIC A: Assessing and improving the acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions for the end users:** this topic aims to evaluate our knowledge about building users' behaviours, expectations and concerns, and how this knowledge should drive the design and implementation of smart solutions.
- **TOPIC B: Solutions for user-centred smart buildings:** this topic aims to investigate the question of integration of all smart technologies that can increase the quality of life of occupants (accessibility, comfort, health, real-time adaptation, etc...)
- **TOPIC C: Responsive and engaged end users of smart buildings:** this topic aims to investigate how smart technologies can trigger behavioural changes among end users to serve other purposes than their own quality of life (building operation optimization, resource efficiency, etc).

The present White Paper focusses on the first topic, i.e. “**Acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions**”. It presents the outcomes of a collective work carried out by the members of the Task Force, from March to June 2021. Paced by series of online workshops, the following steps were addressed:

- Definition of scope
- Review of the State of the Art and identification of the points, in particular those requiring more detailed inquiries
- Analysis of barriers and drivers
- Identification of R&I gaps.

The final aim of this White Paper is to feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on smart buildings that will be produced by the SmartBuilt4EU consortium by mid-2023, together with some recommendations targeting policy makers.

2. Topic under investigation by the Task Forces

2.1. Rationale

Smart building solutions are a strong leverage for increased energy efficiency in buildings, improved quality of life for occupants and added value for work performance, but only if those solutions are correctly understood and adopted by end users. While numerous smart solutions are being developed for the building sector, they are often designed following a technology-push approach, insufficiently taking into account the actual behaviours of building users and occupants, their expectations in terms of building features and functionalities, but also their reluctance or fears related to Information technologies, in particular the loss of privacy and control.

A smart building can be – from a technological perspective – easily defined as list of technological solutions implemented (and potentially interacting) in the building, referring for example to the systems and services that would further be assessed based on the Smart Readiness Indicator. However, from the user's perspective a particular element of smartness could be highly valued in smart office building, but not accepted in a private home. Additionally, a given smart functionality could also be differently accepted by different users in the same building.

Hence, the acceptability of a smart building not only depends on a technical solution, but also largely depends on establishing good relations and interactions between occupants and other involved stakeholders. The energy savings and other expected impacts of smart building technologies strongly relate to the acceptance, as well as actual and proper use of these solutions. These are preconditions to ultimately achieve the optimal performance of the building. Exploring and designing the overall feeling (in terms of acceptance, comfort, well-being, etc.) of occupants is a key to the success of any smart building.

Increasing our knowledge and understanding of end users' wishes, expectations, behaviours and uncertainties is therefore a key success factor to develop fit-for-use smart building products and systems that really meet their markets. Indeed, different profiles of end users require different solutions and trigger different reactions and behaviours (early adopters vs change-adverse people). A sharper sociological and market knowledge of end users shall enable more customized products, but also more efficient co-design workflows and engagement processes. Also, a lot can be learnt from the IT consumer goods sector (communication, entertainment) on how to increase the attractiveness of smart solutions for the building applications.

Therefore, this white paper aims to provide an overview on what is known and what should be further investigated to answer the following questions:

- What is our state of knowledge on building users' expectations, preferences and behaviours?
- Which of their specificities constitute major barriers or success factors to design fit-for-use smart building products?
- What technical and non-technical solutions can increase the acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions?

2.2. Vision: How can a smart building be attractive to end users?

To ensure maximum attractiveness and acceptance of end-users, the smart building shall:

- Provide easy-to-get-and-grab information on **how to use** the building to end users.

- Provide **monitoring feedback to end users**, i.e. customised information how the building operates, how the operational conditions are perceived by the occupants, and how occupants behaviours can impact the building performances. Feedback includes energy usage, indoor environmental quality, health related parameters, appliances usage data, etc. Information can be given through simple visualisation of data monitoring, historical trend analysis, specific widgets or ad hoc suggestions. Such feedback should include quantitative indicators such as saved kWh.
- **Provide recommendations** to users and facility managers for improved building operations, or according to their preferences (energy savings, comfort, air quality), e.g. giving advice on window opening and/or blind/shade moving to improve the thermal environment.
- **Dynamically adapt the building operation** to end-user preferences and behaviours. This means both learn from the end-user behaviours and actuate accordingly on building equipment.
- **Allow override when necessary**, i.e. enable the user to steer the system/building on its own in specific cases.
- Enable the above-mentioned information exchanges with the end user through **simple, user friendly interfaces**, that are **inclusive** to all population at any time in life (hence avoiding technological divide).

Figure 6: Smartness requirements for the attractiveness of smart buildings to end users

2.3. Scope

As figure 2 shows, three main blocks of knowledge are deemed most relevant to identify pathways towards an increased acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions.

Figure 7: The three building blocks of Topic A

A. Knowledge of users: understanding of social behaviours and market knowledge

This block includes the strategies to drive the acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions and to plan solutions for user-centred smart buildings. This requires a clear view of the typology of end-users. Different aspects of typologies should be researched. These aspects include:

- Typologies related to **occupants needs and usage of the smart building**, resulting in different technical requirements: living vs working in the building, people with disabilities, older people with evolving needs...
- **Role/position of end-user in decision making process** of smart building design. Multi apartment buildings, for instance, are often designed considering economic viability of smart solutions, while the actual future occupants are not involved in this process. For a small – private house – where the investor is also the future occupant, this can be completely different.
- **Individual perceptions of well-being** with regard to the building use. The concept of the human well-being as a social and psychological state represents emotional response of the person to the environment (i.e. to the multitude of physical conditions) or situation (i.e. multitude of social conditions) in which individual is involved.
- **Attitudes towards environmental concerns** such as energy efficiency, environmental protection, circular economy.
- Acceptance and **attitude towards smart technologies**, and abilities to use them (i.e. taking in account the “technological divide”). To better understand the social behaviour or user acceptance, knowledge is needed about which determinants relate to the technology acceptance of users.

B. Workflows and communication to raise acceptance and attractiveness

This block relates to the workflows enabling the involvement of end users in the design and adoption of smart solutions:

- **Product and system design:** what are the best practices in terms of end users involvement in the design processes?
- **Communication strategies:** what are the best practices in terms of awareness raising campaigns, showcases, customized communication in order to increase the level of knowledge and trust of users?

C. Technical solutions to raise acceptance and attractiveness

This block relates to the technical solutions that can foster the interest of end-users in smart building features, with a particular focus on:

- **Human User Interface:** How to make the best use of mobile apps, of user-specific dashboards and consolidated interfaces to facilitate and increase the volume and quality of interactions with users?
- **Gamification:** how can the gamification approach (i.e. the introduction of game principles in non-game contexts) be used in the smart building sector? Where and how is it relevant?

3. State of the Art

3.1. State of the Art from EC-funded projects

Most literature and data available regarding the three knowledge blocks defined above come from:

- Projects targeting energy efficiency in buildings, mostly with a focus on the development and demonstration of smart solutions and strategies for behavioural change, and including to that end some analysis of end user behaviours and the related influencing factors
- “Healthy ageing” and “aging in place” projects relating to the new requirements in the living environment for the ageing population
- IoT-driven projects, mainly “technology-push”, which address in a peripheric manner the questions of end user perceptions on IoT
- Smart city projects which address the issues of awareness raising, acceptance and stakeholders’ engagement in smart city projects (mostly with deep renovation focus).

Figure 8: Overview of European projects screened by the Task Force for Topic A

A. Knowledge of users: understanding of social behaviours and market knowledge

Building requirements for ageing population is quite well covered by European projects ([HOMES4LIFE](#), [ACTIVAGE](#)), although they do not fully address the friendliness of user interfaces and user confidence in these systems. HOMES4LIFE developed a certification framework for age-friendly buildings, in collaboration with end users. ACTIVAGE defined “Requirement specification for ageing well” based on user-centered design methods, and will produce building users’ behavioural analysis based on IoT home sensors. The [AAL](#) (Active and Assisted Living) programme stimulated the development of an age-tech sector in Europe with a better understanding of the market segments.

A number of EC-funded projects analyses **building users’ behaviours and influencing factors in different buildings** (mainly tertiary) and deliver specifications for IT product development, strategies to influence behaviours in view of improved energy efficiency of buildings ([MOBISTYLE](#), [E-TEACHER](#), UNIFY-IoT, [S3C](#), [TwinENERGY](#), [CulturalE](#)). E-Teacher provides a very detailed analysis of end-users behaviours on their pilot buildings, which include residential buildings, offices, health care centers and schools, covering both public and private buildings and a wide range of building user types. MOBISTYLE changes the paradigm “Buildings consume energy” to “People use energy” and shifts its focus from buildings and technologies to people behaviour, habits and practices. CulturalE looks at climate and socio-cultural differences in the use of residential buildings around Europe to establish guidelines for designing Plus Energy Buildings taking into account those differences.

H2020 Smart city projects ([SMARTER TOGETHER](#), [MY SMART LIFE](#)...) address the issues **of awareness raising and stakeholder engagement** and the role of ICT-based solutions in this process, but with a total focus on smart city projects (not single building usage).

Technology acceptance

The most prominent approach to quantify technology acceptance is the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Fred Davis. The model argues that perceived usefulness of a technology, which is “the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance”, and ease of use, which is “the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would be free of physical and mental effort”.

Figure 9: The Technology Acceptance Model, Venkatesh & Davis, 2000

Davis, in 1985, determine people’s attitude towards adopting technology. The attitude towards adoption in turn predicts the actual adoption of a certain technology. Perceived usefulness and ease of use are affected

by certain external variables and ease of use affects perceived usefulness. Davis, Bagozzi and Warshav (1989) add the variable behavioral intention and explain that intention is mostly influenced by the attitude towards using technology and is the best predictor of the actual use.

Even though the TAM proves to be helpful in explaining technology adoption, critics argue that more variables are needed. The so-called TAM2 has been developed by Venkatesh and Davis (see Figure 9) adds social influence processes (subjective norm, voluntariness, and image) and cognitive instrumental processes (job relevance, output quality, result demonstrability and perceived ease of use) to the original TAM. In addition to acceptance, attractiveness or enjoyment is examined as well, while acceptance could also be related to contributing to a certain value. A value can be energy-saving or reducing CO₂ or something else. The technology acceptance behaviour of users can be influenced by positive or negative loaded determinants. Positive determinants are motivations, compatibility connectedness, and control while negative determinants are hindrance and cost. Motivations and hindrance are internal factors whereas connectedness compatibility, control, and cost are external factors. Compatibility and connectedness relate to the willingness or intention to use (ease of use) while also contributing to business and market directions to enhance the use of technologies (Park et, al, 2017). Furthermore, we must distinguish between users' behaviour of acceptance of technologies and user's adoption of technologies. In executing research and innovation projects this needs to be kept in mind. This applies specially to ageing adults, which have been less exposed to technologies such as IoT.

B. Workflows and communication and C. Technical solutions to raise acceptance and attractiveness

User-centered design: Smart Building technology acceptance can be increased through a strong and cautious involvement of users from the initial design stages. Design can refer here to new buildings/projects initiatives as well as to initiatives associated with the deployment of smart systems in existing buildings.

As stated in the ISO 9241-210 (Human-centred design for interactive systems) ('Ergonomics of human-system interaction ISO 9241-210', 2010) a user-centred approach *"is an approach to interactive systems development that aims to make systems usable and useful by focusing on the users, their needs and requirements, and by applying human factors / ergonomics, and usability knowledge and techniques. This approach enhances effectiveness and efficiency, improves human well-being, user satisfaction, accessibility and sustainability; and counteracts possible adverse effects of use on human health, safety and performance."*

As far as "experience" is concerned, (Alben, 1996) defines it as the *"aspects of how people use an interactive product: the way it feels in their hands, how well they understand how it works, how they feel about it while they're using it, how well it serves their purposes, and how well it fits into the entire context in which they are using it"*.

It is in this framework that a lot of efforts are being devoted towards the creation of a consumer-centric approach to smart building solutions. Two complementary approaches are highlighted below.

1. Increasing user voluntariness through feedback, engagement and proactivity.

In this framework technologies have been widely used for human user interface, gamification, training and smart feedbacks in a reasonable timeframe.

Gamification apps aim at behavioural change regarding optimal building operation and use and/or at creating awareness on the associated health benefits. The use of a range of Gamification principles - such as rewards for daily use, social comparison, challenges and 'unlocking' extra features as progress is made – offers a real promise in terms of increased attractiveness and future acceptability. A typical approach is a series of gamified challenges, designed following a project's people centric approach: this has been put in

practice in a EU H2020 projects like MOBISTYLE in residential demonstration cases, eTEACHER where recommendations and missions were tailored to the specific users, with social comparison possible via a ranking of those acting on the recommendations, comparing individual's position with their neighbours or colleagues. One can also mention the French regional project Ecoffices, aiming at making employees (in office buildings) aware of the topic of energy savings:

- Measurable actions can be captured by sensors within the environment. The game identifies different behaviours within the home or office, based on data collected from the sensors available.
- Based on the analysis of the data, the game provides incentives in the form of recognition, achievements and suggestions with the ultimate goal to encourage the users to adopt and sustain particular behaviours towards better energy efficiency and also provide useful health tips.

Crowdsensing should also be mentioned here, which refers to the crowdsourcing of sensor data from mobile devices. This technique involves a large group of individuals having mobile devices capable of sensing and computing (e.g. smartphones, tablets, etc) who collectively share data and extract information to measure, map, analyze, estimate or infer any processes of common interest. This technique could have a lot of potential for smart buildings, in particular regarding energy efficiency and air quality. While no EU project is yet identified as exploring this technique for buildings, the EC-funded project [Crowd4Roads](#) aims to apply crowd sensing and ride sharing to road applications.

2. Co-design processes between technological developers and final end-users in or order to design solutions that are more fit-for-use.

Co-design is meant as an approach which actively involves all stakeholders in the design process to help ensure the result meets their needs and is usable. While some studies highlight the potential of codesign, others are more sceptical pointing to a lack of clarity over how the involvement of customers affects the design process and outcomes.

Co-design is for instance applied in the [INTERCONNECT](#) project to design demand response solutions in buildings, in [SMARTER TOGETHER](#) project to deliver smart and inclusive solutions, or in the [ACTIVAGE](#) project to develop smart services for ageing in place. ACTIVAGE applied user-centric design methods combining documentary analysis, open questionnaires, structured and semi-structured interviews and focus groups. To develop the [MOBISTYLE](#) solutions, a people-centred methodology, where users are kept in the development loop through an iterative approach combining, questionnaires, focus groups, workshops and observations, was used to ensure that people's behaviour and habits are influenced. Co-design workshops were used within eTEACHER to generate design recommendations for an ICT tool which met the needs of multiple building stakeholders and utilized Feedback Forums throughout the development and demonstration phase of the tool to continue end-user involvement in refining the tool design.

3.2. Other initiatives and innovations

Other initiatives and innovations provide significant achievements.

- LIST launched a research project entitled Post Occupancy Evaluation SYstem ([POESY](#)), to tackle issues surrounding uncomfortable or inefficient buildings. The system collects feedback from occupants, data from sensors, connects them to the Building Information Model and gives a centralised overview of a building. It will then be compared to what the architects and engineers planned in their simulation before construction to achieve a certain set of parameter performance.

- At Monash University (AUS), [Co-Design for Healthy Ageing](#), a cross-cultural and cross-generational student project using co-design methodology with elders, allowed to open minds of the students who created empathetic solutions for healthy ageing.
- The theme of the National Disability Authority's Research Promotion Scheme in 2017 was progressing lifetime communities through a Universal Design lens. In response to this theme, an investigation into the [Universal Design of Fall Detection Technologies](#) and their impact on lifetime communities was undertaken by the University of Cork (Ireland) together with its partners. One of the objectives was to investigate how smart home and fall detection technologies can be better integrated into communities' everyday life. A need for standards, policy change and improved interoperability across a range of smart technologies is highlighted.
- In their position paper "[How to make green and healthy housing affordable for all consumers](#)" the BEUC proposes initiatives to address the different barriers consumers face when considering retrofitting their homes. To address the lack of awareness, clear information should be provided. As an example, BEUC recommends that Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) should be less technical, easier to read and display more practical information for consumers and installers. EPCs should integrate information from the local market to become more accurate and more consistent. Other BEUC's recommendations target one-stop-shop's organisation as front- and back- office services.
- The Sustainability in Business Lab (SUS.Lab) completed in 2019 a project addressing the [Digitalization in the Building sector](#). In this project, two documents were published: an industry report providing a comprehensive overview of the latest digital technologies penetrating the building industry and a white paper summarizing the policy implications and providing best-practices recommendations for technology developers and users. In addition, they have developed an interactive negotiation game for policy makers, businesses and researchers where participants negotiate the adoption of a particular digital building technology.
- The [EDGE Next platform](#), developed by the real estate EDGE, uses big data and smartness of smart buildings to optimise office building's performance, making it healthier and more sustainable but also to optimise the experience for the occupants by offering valuable and actionable insights (optimising the space, enhancing the health of a team, reducing energy consumption).

3.3. Good practices and lessons learnt

The main lessons learnt based on the above State of the Art can be synthesized as follows:

A. Knowledge of end users

- Needs and expectations of elderly people in buildings are now well documented and translated into technical requirements that can be applied to smart building solutions.
- Theoretical tools to model the technology acceptance can be applied to the smart building research field, but they do not yet capture properly the gap between of acceptance and adoption/use
- Smart building solutions must be customised and marketed to different user profiles (age, type of dwelling, geography/culture; 'technological divide')
- Smart building solutions must be designed differently for residential and non-residential buildings (for the same people: different needs, different expectations, different fears)

B. Workflows and communication

- Co-design processes are highly relevant ‘on principle’ and currently developed/tested in EU projects with some very promising first results, but their replicability & effectiveness are not yet evaluated
- The end user must be educated on how to use and benefit from smart building solutions. For instance:
 - Education is successful in Peer2Peer sessions in which ageing people give information and instruction to other older people.
 - Session should be organized in which older people can experience a smart building solution and in which they can train their skills to use the solution.

C. Technical solutions

- Human User Interfaces, gamification processes, ‘tangible interactions’ when fit-for-use, have a real and measurable impact on user behaviours for energy efficiency.
- The ability to customize such interfaces according to personal preferences is a key point to increase their use by building occupants. Proposing HUI options of native languages and graphical visualisation of data are a must.
- The volume and selection of information provided to the end user is also critical

The next paragraphs illustrate more specifically some of these findings based on the analysis of the EU projects mentioned above.

A. Knowledge of end users:

- The eTeacher project developed some detailed ***analysis framework and data collection process*** to study building occupant’s behaviour and in relation to their IT devices, in order to document their pilot buildings. The data include energy-related behaviours and awareness, information that users would be ready to share with others (energy bills, tips for energy savings, etc.), sources of discomfort (temperature, natural light, etc.), personal inclinations to perform energy savings (economic & environmental drivers, easiness of implementation, ...), preferred methods to get user’s attention on energy saving schemes, etc. This shows great potential for replication.
- The Cultural-E project has developed the ***European Climate and Cultural Atlas for Plus Energy Building Design*** – the 2CAP-Energy Atlas, an online tool to help designers, researchers and policy makers to understand how different European climates and cultures can influence energy demand in buildings. This GIS tool allows users to focus the development efforts on appropriate technologies throughout the context analysis based upon local climate factors and all the important cultural factors associated with building occupants.
- The ACTIVAGE and HOMES4LIFE documented precisely the needs of elderly people and translated them in clear requirements that can be re-used for further development of smart solutions related to ageing, and more largely also to take account of elderly people’s expectation when designing smart building solutions.

B. Workflows and communication

- The ACTIVAGE project succeeded in implementing some co-design process for “healthy ageing” solutions that involved very different stakeholders - doctors, social services, carers, technicians, policy makers, citizens.
- The eTeacher project builds upon the literature and some stakeholders workshops to provide a set of recommendations for the design of ICT-based engagement of end-user for energy efficiency in buildings.

- The MOBISTYLE project has succeeded in changing behaviour regarding energy consumption and well-being in its Slovenian demo by involving users not only in the design of the solutions but also in designing communication campaigns for a long-lasting effect. **Minimalistic solutions seemed to work better**: the more information people get, the more they seem to dislike the solution and vice versa. The SmarterTogether project collaborates with locally anchored partner to help reach a broader audience in regard to citizen's participation in "Energy Savings café", Urban Living Lab, workshops, school classes working on smart projects, and contribute in a very interactive way to different small tasks and discussions facilitating the co-creation processes.
- **Peer-to-peer knowledge exchange network** played a key role as well in the co-creation of user-centric smart city solutions and allowed to exceed most of the initial objectives. This process aims at integrating the expertise of local businesspeople, neighbourhood communities and initiatives, local politicians and policy makers.
- To increase the level of knowledge and trust of users, a **storytelling approach** in producing informative materials to engage people in different demo cases was developed and use in the MOBISTYLE project.
- Cost-effective and simple multi-channel campaigns can be very effective. The MOBISTYLE project has found that a simple but persistent approach is relevant, and that complex data gathering is not necessary in all cases and circumstances.

B. Technical solutions

As exemplified by Paulus Schoutsen in a [post](#), a good system (and any of its components) should:

- first of all never fail, but if it does, it should not put the user in trouble - *what will be the impact if the system suddenly doesn't work?* – with ideally the capacity of the system to fall back to a previous configuration, even if considered 'less smart';
- not lessen the user comfort and easiness he/she is used - indeed not focus on changing life, but on adapting and improving it, and in fact seamlessly "blend with the user current workflow"
- offer easy and natural ways of interaction – including voice interfaces or any intuitive 'physical' interaction
- offer a local implementation of the system with easy and quick means of correcting it, with the cloud being treated as an extension to your smart building system instead of running it, and with a way to decide which data are to ship over the cloud and which are not.

Regarding Human User interfaces:

- The **possibility for users to use different devices** (smartphone, tablet, laptop) improves their experience.
- Besides graphical apps and games, users shall not only be informed but also sufficiently consulted, trained and supported regarding the technological changes to avoid poor performance in practice. KPIs should be easy-to-understand.
- The **delay** from physical event associated with human-building interaction and the information presented in the ICT-based solution is crucial. If this delay is longer than e.g. 30 minutes, the actual use and perceived value of provided information is questionable.
- The capacity to **easily customise** dashboards is instrumental in the deployment and use of these tools towards the users. In all cases, providing graphical apps and games in the users' native language is mandatory (principle of localisation).
- Another important point is to enable users to enter building-specific target behaviours into the app, to take into account local issues and opportunities.
- Identify the **appropriate level of quantitative information** to be provided, inducing a more technical look & feel to the user interface away from the more user-friendly (even fun!) feature initially desired to attract / convince people.
- **Tangible interaction concept and tangible devices**: Weingarten and Albayrak (2011) introduced the idea of "tangible information visualization in smart homes environments". It aims at providing tangible (i.e.

physically sensed) feedback to the occupants of a smart environments. In their work, a vibrating wristband provides feedback on energy consumption. Besides the idea itself, tangible interaction might help in connecting building monitoring and automation to the occupants. A tangible tabletop, for instance, is known as a useful mean to collectively make decisions. Those technologies and applications might be efficient in smart building environments as well, especially as collective spaces are concerned. Interacting with tangible objects, within a group of users, can help them understand the purpose of human behaviours against building efficiency goals and ultimately inform building systems on the best way to regulate, or the accepted boundaries in relation with e.g. occupant comfort.

4. Barriers and drivers for the increased acceptance and adoption of smart building solutions by end users

4.1. Barriers

The number of factors to consider, moreover of different nature (e.g. the evolution over the whole life, various community models, different levels of technology adoption, etc.), makes those issues of awareness and even more acceptance of smart buildings and their technologies intrinsically complex. As such the integration of different technologies should lead to a level of automation offering indeed various functionalities and service-levels focussing on naturel and evolving/adapting interaction between the users and their home, keeping in mind there one system is not going to fit all. This requires considering a complex ecosystem that encompasses the user and his/her home (and potentially the surrounding environment), with time to converge to an optimum depending on varying needs and constraints.

The figure below synthesises the main barriers identified to the increased acceptance and adoption of smart building solutions by end users

TECHNICAL	Weak adaptability of buildings to different end-users`profiles and to their different life phases in the building (e.g. moving in, getting used to the equipment...)	} Top barriers according to the Task Force
ECONOMIC	Economic concerns for end-user, occupant, private investor and owner: affordability/short term, compared to benefits (medium to long-term)	
SOCIAL	Fears related to lack of data privacy and lack of control on smart solutions Unknown, different perceptions of comfort for different end-users wrt smart building use	
VALUE CHAIN	Lock-in effect: how the smart solutions will evolve in the future, requirements for updates, upgrades Difficulties to implemented successful co-design processes with end-users in order to develop more user-centered products	

Figure 10: Overview of main barriers

Additional comments regarding the barriers shown in Figure 4:

- Weak adaptability of buildings to different end-users’ profiles: this also includes the weak management of different behaviour of users through the life cycle of the smart building, from moving into building, with its learning phase (intensive interactions with smart building systems), and use-phase where interactions/active use is minimised.
- Economic concerns for end-user, occupant, private investor and owner: the issue is the affordability on the short term, compared to benefits that are driven by the medium to long-term. It also related to the costs of smart building design and implementation, the perceived value of smart building for market attractiveness of the building, compared with, for example location, and/or other parts of value proposition.
- The Lock-in effect might gain more awareness in the future: for instance, the bankrupts of some equipment/ service providers will lead to missing (software) product updates for the end users.

4.2. Drivers

The figure below synthesises the main drivers identified to increase the acceptance and adoption of smart building solutions by end users.

Figure 11: Overview of main drivers

Three additional comments regarding the drivers shown in Figure 5:

- Leverage on specific groups of people with most interest in providing feedback on SB solutions, like elderly people (smart solutions may compensate for some of the functional/mental decline): looking for a feeling of safety & security when ageing, health and self-esteem will be high on the agenda of the ageing population. Furthermore, they wish to age-in-place. Not in all residential building this is possible whereas at the same time ageing people seek for a safe and comfortable environment. Smart technologies that are easy to install and to understand that has functionalities such as safe entrance, burglary alarm, surveillance cameras can support older people to age-in-place.
- New approaches in user-centred design, such as design thinking, co-creation processes, [mental models](#) considerations. User-centred design (UCD) means that designers set out to create a product that reflects the user needs and preferences à Drivers like respecting the mental models of users, carrying out a thorough usability test and observing plenty of users interacting with product – can make a real difference, helping above all designers to create products that work with users, that speak the user’s language.
- COVID-19 effect operates as an accelerator for increasing smart readiness in existing buildings (increased awareness in relation with indoor air quality)

5. Research & Innovation Gaps

The next sections list a set of gaps and topics for further investigation, as identified by the task force members, regarding:

- Research and development topics to increase acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions to end users
- Go-to-market topics such as Certification / standardization, regulation, scaling up and industrialisation.

5.1. Research & Development gaps

Topic: User needs and behaviours

- **Include aging as evolving parameter to design building controls and interfaces:** as we grow older our bodies change, and so do our habits and perceptions. What we once might have perceived as “cold” is not “comfortable” and the time we need to learn a new skill changes as well. These parameters shall be taken into account while optimizing the building operational conditions (e.g. smart thermostats, smart lightings etc) as well as when presenting outputs to users of different ages.
- Perform **consolidated return on experience regarding co-creation processes** and valorise the outcome to the end users: what (in past projects and experience) was the actual user's influence on final design? How to show them that they have impact?
- **Study potential conflicts between users' behaviours, wellness feelings and engagement, and benefits for energy saving or climate adaptation.** Building performance requirements could be conflicting with desired functional needs. Especially when these concerns functional needs from ageing people. Furthermore, building performance requirements targeting at climate adaptations solutions could lead to unplanned effects (e.g. Use of certain plants could act as a bio-irritantia or allergen component, or the water parts in buildings could be a perfect place for mosquitoes to grow).
- **Account for the dynamics in technology innovations fitting users' needs and competencies:** the uptake of technological innovations are rapid and these might exceed the speed of technology acceptance/ adoption. According to the innovation model of Rogers, innovators will be followed by early adopters after which the majority (first an early group followed by a late group) will follow. Users will need to have time to accept and adopt a proposed smart building technology. This account for both users as for engineers (installers).
- Investigate the **fast evolution of behaviours, perceptions and expectations of the next generation of users** (millennial, generation Alpha) in their relation to information, communication and automation technologies.
- Investigate how **the pandemics affected behaviours of building users**, how smart buildings can respond to such changes and provide more **resilience** for potential future pandemics or other types of crisis.

Topic: Intelligent software development

- Explore how to integrate **recommender systems for energy-efficient smart buildings**. Such systems have significantly developed in recent years in parallel with the witnessed advancements in both

internet of things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. But despite their success in different research and development applications (e.g. in healthcare, online shopping, movies, music, travel plans, etc.), there is still room for more research to improve their performance, especially in the energy saving domain. The application of recommender systems in the building energy sector is a very promising field since it does not only recommend energy saving actions but can also be extended to help consumers acquire appliances

- **Explore beyond building digital twin to enable new occupancy models.** Examples from industrial sectors where Digital Twins are more advanced (e.g. manufacturing) shall be leveraged to increase the flexibility of building. Digital Twins and potentially introducing an orchestrating entity managing different instances of building digital twins to enable "Building as a Service" - i.e. adapting the behaviour of a building and its interaction with the user based on the setting. This includes the further development of intuitive and self-learning (AI-based) systems
- **Tackle human and data biases (race, gender, age, etc) in AI technologies** applied to smart buildings. A famous illustration is the case of car voice recognition system not recognizing a female voice. If un-researched and unaddressed, this can be a major barrier to acceptability and uptake of smart building solutions.
- Develop systems to **collect human feedback on comfort perception all along the occupation phases** in a non-disruptive manner. Indeed, building managers are facing the need to smoothly understand the satisfaction of their occupants in order to provide the highest comfort while balancing with energy consumption. Moreover, manual and mechanical ventilation are key to healthy indoor environments. Research is required to understand those trade-offs amongst ventilation & air recycling and energy consumption, relying on users in a non-intrusive manner. Semantic models (e.g. BIM), sensing devices and assessment methodologies (e.g. Life-Cycle Assessment) are still to be developed. It is worth mentioning that such systems might contribute to reporting on IAQ and comfort in the context of recent building certification frameworks (e.g. WELL¹, FITWELL²), which require life-long monitoring of indoor conditions and occupants satisfaction for the maintenance of the certification.

Topic: Demonstration of business models and governance forms

- Explore new business models related to smart solutions supporting **assisted living**.
- Explore how the **data produced** in the smart buildings can feed new business models.
- Explore **governance models for cross domain data sharing** in a safe and value- added way, larger scale integrations across sectors for services stacking, infrastructure sharing between different stakeholders.

Topic: System integration and Demo-level with communities

- Leverage on existing **energy communities**: several small and bigger communities already exist and they automatically cluster stakeholders who are more willing to contribute to smart building information. They can be taken as trailblazers for future projects demonstration.

Topic: Dynamic knowledge of users

¹ <https://www.wellcertified.com>

² <https://www.fitwel.org>

- Develop **capability of smart buildings to differentiate types of users**, e.g. gender, age, task, location in the building and so on, and provide guidelines and support accordingly (i.e. the smart building adapts to user and not the other way around).
- Develop **one-button system gathering daily feedback from users** to give input to adapt building systems - low-threshold- easy to use devices and or ambient learning to interpret behaviour for optimal building service settings. User interfaces should be kept as simple, meaning easy to use as possible to enhance acceptance, therefore building designers and engineers should strive to develop one-button systems.

5.2. Go-to-market gaps

Topic: Certification / standardization

- Further UI standardisation for **users with handicaps or special needs**, building on the work of the Homes4Life project
- **Standardisation of user interfaces** for all providers of smart building solutions and APIs to allow multiple solutions/services to be connected and visualised in a user specific dashboard/interface, building on the work of the DIGIPLACE project.
- There is a gap in relation with **calibration means and accuracy of (sensing) devices** in view of data sharing amongst smart building service providers. For the time-being the industry lacks clear standards that would enable higher long-term, interoperability amongst sensing infrastructures and other smart building services.

Topic: Regulation

- There is a need for clear and protective (EU-based data hosting) **data management policies**: how can we create trust in smart solutions in buildings with respect to data privacy? European level (or at least national level) regulation demanding data collectors and data providers to ensure data security and allow for transparent access to authorised stakeholders.
- Include **"Open Source" regulations**, requiring any device/application that will not be maintained to release publicly its core functionalities/source code to make it upgrade-able. In other words, if the owner of a certain technology is not willing to maintain it anymore the technology shall be made public so that legacy can be guaranteed for existing applications, avoiding vendor lock in consumers strong-arming.

Topic: Scaling up & industrialisation

- **Identify real benefits for users** so that they have a clear idea of what they get for the money, as well as the co-benefits (in addition to the SRI) as identified in SmatBuilt4EU WP3 on comfort, health, etc... and € of course.
- **Explore potential market disruptions** in relation with very large **players from the IT sector** potentially entering the building market. Indeed, European industry players, either well established and start-ups, face a medium-term challenge associated with the potential stronger positioning of very larger player (Google, Apple, Facebook, Amazon) in the smart-building market. This would significantly influence the business models, in particular in relation with services to end-users.
- Explore how smart buildings can qualify with regard to the [EU Taxonomy for sustainable investments](#), as a driver for smart building investments.

- Ensure that smart building concepts are taken up by the [New Bauhaus initiative](#), as viable green, sustainable investment.

6. Conclusions

This document formalises the collaborative work performed by the members of SmartBuilt4EU task force 1, on a voluntary basis, during the period March - June 2021. It also integrates the feedback collected during 1) a peer review conducted by VITO in June 2021, and 2) an open consultation process during in July – August 2021. Based on an analysis of the state of the art and the identification of barriers and drivers, the main objective of this paper is to detect some Research and Innovation gaps that still need to be addressed in the coming years in order to foster the end user acceptance and attractiveness of smart building solutions. This White Paper will feed the elaboration of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda that the SmartBuilt4EU consortium will present to the European Commission.

Task Force 1 will investigate two more topics during 2021 – 2022: next topic, starting October 2021, will focus on the **user-centred building**, i.e. the integration of smart solutions for enhanced well-being, inclusiveness and health of occupants.

If you have some expertise to share on this topic, you are invited to join the task force and contribute to the next White Paper (contact detail below).

To receive the updates on the SmartBuil4EU task forces, White Papers and events, please register here:
<https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/join-our-community/>

Contact point for Task Force 1:

Clémentine COUJARD, DOWEL Innovation, clementine.coujard@dowel.eu

Annex 1: list of European projects reviewed

Project	Status	Weblink	Relevant inputs
User behaviour			
	Completed in 2020	https://www.mobistyle-project.eu/en/mobistyle	<p>Analysis of behaviours connected to the use of buildings (italian and slovenian universities). A paper discussing the survey’s findings was published on the ‘EDP Sciences’ website.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for the ICT developers based on focus groups findings. • Development of gamified app and dashboard • Evaluation of campaigns and tools effectiveness on users
	Completed in 2020	http://www.eteacher-project.eu/about-the-project/	SoA on ICT-based engagement for EE; evidence-based approach for developing behaviour change interventions; Case studies of end-user behaviours in buildings
	Completed (FP7)	http://www.s3c-project.eu/	Customer engagement guidelines and tools for EE and smartgrid projects; analysis of critical success factors for consumer involvement in active demand by measuring the performance of technical and non-technical interaction schemes as well as customer awareness initiatives deployed in smart grid pilot projects
	Completed	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/688369/results	D4.3 recommendations for societal and educational aspects and value co-creation mechanisms sustainability
	Ongoing	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957736	Consumer engagement for demand response Home and Tertiary energy monitoring module
	Ongoing	https://eu-phoenix.eu/	Upgrading smartness of existing buildings through innovations for legacy equipment à Develop human-centric approach and training/awareness activities to prepare citizens for smart buildings.
 EE-HIGHRISE	FP7, completed	http://www.ee-highrise.eu/	Analysis of user's behaviour in residential buildings (Project deliverable D4.6), prepared by University of Ljubljana, Faculty of social studies, project partner
 U-CERT User-Centred Energy Performance Assessment and Certification	Ongoing	https://u-certproject.eu/	<p>Applied ethnography research in an interdisciplinary environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tailored research methods and analysis for deep(er) understanding of users’ perception of EPC schemes. - Identification and categorization of results for goal-oriented development of prospective U-CERT services and business models

	Ongoing	www.cultural-e.eu	Cultural and climatic considerations are incorporated into the Plus Energy Building (PEB) designs, aimed at improving the energy post-occupancy energy performance of the building. The work is based on a literature review, the development of an online GIS tool and 4 demonstration cases located in different European climatic regions.
Co-design processes			
	ongoing	https://interconnectproject.eu/	Interoperable solutions connecting smart homes, buildings and grids. à co-creations processes with end-users planned in each demo, design thinking
Smart city projects			
	ongoing	https://www.smarter-together.eu/	Deliverables on urban living lab and co-design processes for Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement (Vienna) in smart city projects
	ongoing	https://www.mysmartlife.eu	Analysis of key Issues for Social Awareness and Acceptance of smart city projects/ ICT case study; Benchmark of ICT based solutions for citizen engagement
s			
	Completed in 2020	http://www.homes4life.eu/	Requirements and specifications for age-friendly housing; taxonomy, KPIs and proposal of certification scheme
ACTIVAGE 	completed	https://www.activageproject.eu/	Objective to provide a co-creation framework enabling to identify, measure, understand and predict the demands and needs of IoT ecosystem on Active & Healthy Ageing users
	Completed in 2020	http://www.aal-europe.eu/	Funding programme that aims to create better quality of life for older people and to strengthen industrial opportunities in the field of healthy ageing technology and innovation. Success stories are provided.

Annex 2: References

- Oppl, Stefan, and Christian Stary. 2014. "Facilitating Shared Understanding of Work Situations Using a Tangible Tabletop Interface." *Behaviour & Information Technology* 33 (6): 619–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2013.833293>.
- Weingarten, Florian, and Sahin Albayrak. 2011. "Feeling Home - Tangible Information Visualization in Smart Home Environments in Relation to the Concept of Transhumanism." *Communications in Computer and Information Science* 174 CCIS (PART 2): 262–66. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22095-1_54.
- O'Flynn, Jane & Pesch, Dirk & Mulvihill, Patrick & Delaney, Kieran & Hayes, Sarah & O Keeffe, Michelle. 2019. *Investigation of the Universal Design of Fall Detection Technologies in the Smart Home and their Impact on Lifetime Communities*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337759974_Investigation_of_the_Universal_Design_of_Fall_Detection_Technologies_in_the_Smart_Home_and_their_Impact_on_Lifetime_Communities
- Tisov, A.; Podjed, D.; D'Oca, S.; Vetršek, J.; Willems, E.; Veld, P.O. *People-Centred Approach for ICT Tools Supporting Energy Efficient and Healthy Behaviour in Buildings. Proceedings 2017, 1*, 675. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings1070675>
- Serena Zheng, Usanoah Apthorpe, Usamarshini Chetty, Nick Feamster. 2018. User Perceptions of Smart Home IoT Privacy. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1802.08182.pdf>
- G. Fico, J. Montalva, A. Medrano, N. Liappas, A. Mata-Díaz, G. Cea and M.T. Arredondo. [Co-creating with consumers and stakeholders to understand the benefit of Internet of Things in Smart Living Environments for Ageing Well: the approach adopted in the Madrid Deployment Site of the ACTIVAGE Large Scale Pilot](#)
- Anastasios A. Economides. 2017. User Perceptions of Internet of Things (IoT) Systems. DOI:[10.1007/978-3-319-67876-4_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-67876-4_1)
- Chankook Park, Yangsoo Kim,, MinJeong. 2018. Influencing factors on risk perception of IoT-based home energy management services. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2018.10.005>
- Ricardo Forgiarini Rupp, Jungsoo Kim, Enedir Ghisi, Richard de Dear. 2019. Thermal sensitivity of occupants in different building typologies: The Griffiths Constant is a Variable. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.07.048>
- Elham Delzendeh, S. Wu, Angela Lee, Ying Zhou. 2017. The impact of occupants' behaviours on building energy analysis: A research review. DOI:[10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.264](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.264)
- Birsel+Seck. 2020. [Co-designing with older people report - a study on aging in America](#).
- Jakob Trischler, Simon J. Pervan, Stephen J. Kelly. 2017. The Value of Codesign: The Effect of Customer Involvement in Service Design Teams.
- Himeura, Abdullah Alsalemia, Ayman Al-Kababjia, Faycal Bensaalia, Abbes Amirab,Christos Sardianosc, George Dimitrakopoulosc, Iraklis Varlamis. 2021. A survey of recommender systems for energy efficiency in buildings: Principles, challenges and prospects. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2021.02.002>
- Mobistyle Deliverables D6.3 Evaluation on the effectiveness of the combined information and feedback campaigns https://www.mobistyle-project.eu/en/mobistyle/dissemination/PublishingImages/public-deliverables/MOBISTYLE_D6.3.pdf

Mobistyle D6.1 Detailed final monitoring, awareness and information campaigns for the five cases https://www.mobistyle-project.eu/en/mobistyle/dissemination/PublishingImages/public-deliverables/MOBISTYLE_D6.1_Nov_2018.pdf

Mobistyle D3.1 Detailed monitoring and information campaign parameters (objectives, data requirements, monitoring tools, information services) based on combined feedback about energy, IEQ and health https://www.mobistyle-project.eu/en/mobistyle/dissemination/PublishingImages/public-deliverables/MOBISTYLE_D3.1.pdf

Verbeke S., Aerts D., Reynders G., Ma Y., Waide P. *Final report on the technical support to the development of a smart readiness indicator for buildings*. June 2020 VITO, Waide https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f9e6d89d-fbb1-11ea-b44f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en?WT.mc_id=Searchresult&WT.ria_c=37085&WT.ria_f=3608&WT.ria_ev=search

Philippe Moseley. 2017. EU Support for Innovation and Market Uptake in Smart Buildings under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/7/4/105>

Maarten De GrooteJonathan VoltFrances Bean (BPIE). 2017. Is europe ready for the smartbuildings revolution? http://bpie.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/STATUS-REPORT-Is-Europe-ready_FINAL_LR.pdf

Legris, Ingham & Collette. 2003. Why do people use information technology? A critical review of the technology acceptance model. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206\(01\)00143-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7206(01)00143-4)

Davis. 1985. A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: theory and results.

Park et Al. 2017. Implications for Training on Smartphone Medication Reminder App Use by Adults With Chronic Conditions: Pilot Study Applying the Technology Acceptance Model. [doi:10.2196/formative.8027](https://doi.org/10.2196/formative.8027)

Alben. 1996. Quality of experience: defining the criteria for effective interaction design. <https://doi.org/10.1145/235008.235010>

ISO 9241-210:2010 Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems. <https://www.iso.org/standard/52075.html>